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MENTALITY AND CULTURAL FEATURES OF FOREIGN STUDENTS

The mentality of a person simply refers to their way of thinking usually as a result of factors such as upbringing, race and ethnic backgrounds. The phrase cultural feature describes distinctive attributes of one's culture and it is closely associated with cultural awareness which is a person's understanding of the differences between themselves and people from other countries or other backgrounds, especially differences in attitudes and values. The society we find ourselves in today is one where more and more trips abroad, short and long study courses and interaction with other cultures across the globe are more prominent than ever. Therefore, it is important to study the nature, mentality and cultural features of international students in order to build understanding and respect amongst people of different cultures.

The mentality or frame of mind of most, if not all international students, is to create an environment in which they feel most at home. Students tend to study in countries which have a common language as theirs for convenience sake. However, on the flip side of that, some students may prefer to study in countries which have a primary language much different from theirs in an attempt to learn a new language as well as a new culture.

There are many distinguishing features that can be used to tell international students apart from the nationals of a country. The first and major feature is language and dialect. There are roughly over 6500 languages spoken across the globe today and so an international student can very easily be identified by the language they speak. In countries where the same primary language as that of the international student is spoken, the problem of difference in dialects may still exist. Dialects mean that even though the language is the same at its core, there are still distinct differences that affect the understanding of both the spoken and written word. As mentioned earlier, some students tend to study in countries which do not speak the same first language or may not have the same dialect as them and these differences may be problematic for the students because it makes learning harder and more inconvenient for them.

Another distinguishing feature is fashion. This is seen more with students of much more traditional backgrounds such as Africans, Indians, Arabs etc. They tend to dress in their national outfits as often as possible for a variety of reasons such as to display pride in their culture and country. Take Nigerian fashion for instance. There are definite distinctions between traditional Nigerian clothing and western clothing in

Nigeria. Traditional clothing signifies which ethnic group one belongs to, and can indicate one's gender, class, religion, tribe and region. For instance, city and rural dwellers in Nigeria can easily distinguish Eastern Nigerian ways of dressing from Northern Nigerian or Western Nigerian ways. This is because the different lifestyles call for different clothing styles.

Furthermore, cultural foods and meals distinguish foreign students from nationals of a country. Studies show that developed countries which import more foreign goods tend to have more international students. Forms of entertainment such as music and dance also help differentiate cultures. Whether it's Afro beats, Pop, or Hip-hop for music or whether it's the salsa dance from Cuba, ballet from Russia, the dragon dance from China, the Zanku dance from Nigeria or even Tango from Argentina for dance, the musical and dance preferences of different nationalities are major distinctive attributes of different foreign students.

Mindsets and mentalities vary drastically from one culture to another and the list of cultural features of foreign students is nearly inexhaustible. The conversation about the mentality and cultural features of foreign students is a very important one mainly because it builds understanding and respect amongst people of different cultures. A proper understanding of this subject fosters healthy student-teacher relationships, business relationships as well as many other kinds of international relationships. Mentalities and cultural features of foreign students will continue to grow more diverse and distinct which make its study very important.

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This article aims at offering a brief summary on the mentality and cultural features of foreign students. This text starts by defining the main terms needed for proper understanding of the topic, and then outlines the unity and coming together of different cultures as a major importance of the study of this topic. Furthermore, distinguishing features such as language and dialect, fashion, cultural foods, and music are highlighted as specific factors which differentiate cultures as well as foreign students from one another. These factors are also used to delve deeper into the cultural diversities of different nationalities. This article ends by establishing the kind of beneficial relationships which can be obtained as a result of proper study of this topic as well as the ever increasing diversity of it.

Keywords: *mentality, cultural, foreign students, distinguishing, feature.*

МЕНТАЛЬНІСТЬ ТА КУЛЬТУРНІ ОСОБЛИВОСТІ ІНОЗЕМНИХ СТУДЕНТІВ

Метою даної статті є короткий огляд менталітету і культурних особливостей іноземних студентів. В тезах визначені основні терміни, необхідні для правильного розуміння теми, описується в загальних рисах

єдність і зближення різних культур як найважливіше значення вивчення цієї теми. Крім того, такі відмітні риси, як мова і діалект, мода, національна їжа та музика, виділені в якості специфічних факторів, які відрізняють культури студентів одну від іншої. Ці фактори також використовуються для більш глибокого вивчення культурних відмінностей різних національностей. У результаті виокремлено вид корисних відносин, які можуть бути отримані в результаті належного вивчення цієї теми, а також її поглиблення.

Ключові слова: *ментальність, культура, іноземні студенти, відмінність, риси*